

Passaging and maintenance of enteroids

Note 1: Mature enteroids (budded with dark lumen), approximately after 5-7 days of culture in CM are ready for passaging. Refer to protocol “Generation of enteroids from fresh porcine jejunum” (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13848853).

Note 2: for the reagents refer to “List of reagents for enteroid protocols” (DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13847508)

- 1) Break the Geltrex™ dome containing enteroids with 200 µL/well ice-cold DMEM/F12 using 1ml pipet tip
- 2) Mechanically dissociate enteroids through pipetting approximately 50 times using a 200 µL tip.
- 3) Spin at 400 rcf for 5' at 4°C
- 4) Discard the supernatant and resuspend the pellet in 70% Geltrex™ in DMEM/F12. Incubate in a tissue culture incubator for 10' so the Geltrex™ polymerizes.

Note: Usually enteroids are passaged 1:4-1:5 to keep a density of 50 enteroids for well in a 24 well culture plate

- 5) Add 500 µL complete medium for each well